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Tehleel Ahmed
Department of Lifesciences,
Barkatullah Vishwavidyalaya
Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh,
India

Shazia T Shah
Department of Lifesciences,
Barkatullah Vishwavidyalaya
Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh,
India

Ascertaining the repercussion of Covid-19 pandemic as malediction and benediction on education system in the union territory of Jammu and Kashmir

Tehleel Ahmed and Shazia T Shah

Abstract

COVID-19 pandemic paralyzed the whole world with such a robust setback that retrieval of such damage will take decades. We have seen several natural disasters, armed conflicts or any other social and political unrest which have disrupted education system in various countries around the world. But the level of educational disruption caused by the Covid-19 pandemic is greater than anything in modern history. Somehow we have seen the impact of Covid-19 pandemic in the positive way also with reference to the surge in usage of digital equipment's and online mode of teaching and learning but affordable and available to only a few learners. But Union territory of Jammu and Kashmir is one of the worst hit state by the Covid-19 pandemic than any other state of India with reference to the disruption in education system. Both Covid-19 pandemic accompanied by the internet shutdowns post abrogation of Article 370 of Indian constitution coincided and lead to the unrecoverable loss of pedagogy affecting millions of students in the Union territory. According to the UNESCO data available nearly 1.6 billion (constituting 91% students) globally have been impacted by the Covid-19 pandemic. The primary purpose of the intended paper is to ascertain the impact of Covid-19 pandemic on the education system in union territory of Jammu and Kashmir.

Keywords: Covid-19, internet blockade, education system, union territory of Jammu and Kashmir, e-learning and teaching

Introduction

Covid-19 pandemic did not spare any corner of the world or any section of the society from its wrath. Although all the sectors of the economy are affected by this pandemic to such an extent that the whole planet earth is paused. From its start and origin in Wuhan, China in December 2019 by the outbreak of this virus whole world and all international health organizations were in such a dilemma that the naming and identification of the virus became a challenge, but towards the ending of December 2019 a strange symptoms of new pneumonia having an unknown cause was reported from Wuhan, a city in the Hubei Province of China. After quite intense research and struggle the root cause of this infections were found to be a new Coronavirus, which was given the name, "2019 Novel Coronavirus" (2019-nCoV). Later International Committee on Taxonomy of Viruses in the February 11, 2020 renamed it as "Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2" (SARS-CoV2). Because this virus has a genetic relationship with Coronavirus SARS-Co-V which instigated the outbreak in year 2002 (WHO, 2020)

Maharashtra, Union territory of Delhi, Karnataka, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh are the worst hit states by Covid-19 and went through complete lockdown for months to prevent the spread of virus. Fortunately the closure of schools and colleges did not entirely stopped the teaching and learning process, but it changed its course from physical to virtual mode, so that the alternative way of education remained in continuous process. Virtual way of learning was assisted by the use of the internet via online classes, e-books, video conferencing, Google-meet, TV, Radio and other digital technologies.

Education system in Union territory of Jammu and Kashmir is worst affected by the nationwide lockdown due to Covid-19 because it was preceded by the mobile internet and even communication blockade when the article 370 giving some autonomous status to Jammu and Kashmir was abrogated by parliament of India on. In the present era internet is

Corresponding Author:
Tehleel Ahmed
Department of Lifesciences,
Barkatullah Vishwavidyalaya
Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh,
India

playing a pivotal role in the education system through digital mode of learning and teaching, but the union territory of Jammu and Kashmir encountered two consecutive restrictions, curfew with communication blockade post article 370 abrogation and covid-19 lockdown. After March 2020 Covid-19 pandemic again took away the opportunity from the students of Jammu and Kashmir to attend physical class rooms. Even the Supreme court of India did not come to the rescue of millions of students, a petition was filed by the Private Schools Association of Jammu and Kashmir, which demanded the restoration of 4G internet services as students of valley were unable to access the online learning classes being held as a result of Covid-19 lockdown, but the supreme court rejected the petition on 11th May 2020. The judgment not only violates ones right to access the internet but also right to education. According to the data available on website www.internetshutdown.in, Kashmir accounts for nearly half of total 413, outages that India has seen since 2012. (THE WIRE, 2020).

Aims and Objectives of The Study

This research paper will emphasize on the following objectives,

- To study how pedagogy is disrupted by Covid-19 and internet shutdowns in Jammu and Kashmir.
- To study how Covid-19 acted as an amplifier in the digitalization of teaching and learning process in union territory of Jammu and Kashmir.
- To envisage the post Covid-19 era of education in union territory of Jammu and Kashmir.

Material and Methods

For the present study content analysis method is being used which is qualitative in nature. Various reports and data

including facts and figures presented in this study are prepared by various government and NGOs on COVID-19 pandemic. Information are collected from various authentic websites. Some journals and e-contents relating to influence of COVID-19 on educational system globally and in UT of Jammu and Kashmir

Discussion

E-learning is playing a pivotal role from the beginning of the Covid-19 pandemic when social distancing and lockdown is the only option for different states of India including Jammu and Kashmir to minimize the spread of virus.

Covid-19 Education- Era In Jammu And Kashmir and Internet Shutdowns

Scenario of education in Jammu and Kashmir is quite different from rest of the states and union territories of India. Jammu and Kashmir faced double lockdown, the first one when the special status of the state was taken away by the parliament of India by the abrogation of article 370 on August 5, 2019, post which complete communication blackout was done by the state administration and all the educational institution was also closed as well. From millions of students so-called right to education was snatched and whole education system remained lifeless for months due to curfew like situations throughout the Jammu and Kashmir. Complete communication and internet services blockade post abrogation of article 370 remained for almost consecutive 213 days up to March 4, 2020, and even after such a long duration only 2G network was allowed that too only on verified SIMs.

Source: Statista

Graph Showing How Internet Shutdown In Jammu And Kashmir Disrupted Education Along With Covid-19 (Maximum In 2020, Peak Era Of Covid-19)

Gradually in the month of March 2020 when educational institutions started coming on track, Covid-19 pandemic stepped in and again educational institutions were closed. As we know that maximum portion of Jammu and Kashmir lies in the mighty Himalayan rang, so the geography of the state is almost hilly and it became much more difficult for the students, and teachers in the rural areas for accessing the modern digital technology during the covid-19 pandemic.

Covid-19 As An Amplifier For Paradigm Shift In The Education System of Jammu and Kashmir

While coping with the Covid-19 learners and the educators started shifting from the traditional physical classrooms to digital mode of learning and teaching.

But this paradigm shift was not too easy for the majority of states including Jammu and Kashmir due to the lack of modern technological and digital tools to avail remote

learning. Nowadays it is a universal fact that, use of modern technology in education has generated new concepts in education system. We are talking about virtual classrooms and various online tools today, that allows interaction between teachers and students exactly like a real or physical class rooms. Throughout the Union Territory, schools are

using existing and available platforms likes of Google Classroom applications, e-libraries and conferencing apps like Zoom, Go To Meeting etc. For students, various engaging resources are available on YouTube, e-libraries, Google, Wikipedia, Yahoo et cetera.

Digital Education A Challenge For Jammu and Kashmir

Covid-19 is a mighty challenge for education system in all the states of India including UT of Jammu and Kashmir. All the states of India are struggling to provide quality education via digital mode. First and foremost difficulty in the online mode of pedagogy is that, neither each and every student has got a mobile phone or a tablet nor everyone can afford the same. But problem faced by Jammu and Kashmir is at another higher level due to 2G mobile internet service and non availability of broadband internet penetration mostly in far flung or rural areas.

Envisaging Education System of Jammu and Kashmir In Post Covid-19 Era

With the closure of educational institutions after the pandemic of covid-19 devastated the whole world, almost all the states of India including Jammu and Kashmir found an alternative way to make available the virtual classrooms to the students, so that, their studies will continue. But the real and virtual education would make a difference in the near future. Millions of children will not return to school. Children whose households have suffered economic shocks due to almost complete lockdown, and girls and young women who are at a high risk of pregnancy, early marriage and gender based violence will be more affected. Expectation of the parents that their children will contribute financially to their families will increase, school going children will be forced into seeking jobs, but this will lead to more school dropouts. According to the survey conducted by the UNESCO covering around 180 countries has projected that 24 million children may not be able to resume their classwork after pandemic. Estimates suggest that more than half of all refugees girls will not return when schools open (World Bank, 2020). Due to pandemic-related learning losses, students currently in school are estimated to face a \$10 trillion reduction in lifetime earnings (WEF, 2020).

Conclusions

The impairment done by the covid-19 in all the sectors of economy, especially in the education system is unprecedented and many glitches we expect to face in the near future will simply be more extreme forms of those that we already face today. The world after covid-19 is unlikely to return to the world that was.

A Blend of digital and traditional learning will increase dramatically

Education system after the Covid-19 is going to be at an upgraded and higher digital level. Most educationists believe that days of passive learning will be over, use of new and advanced technology for teaching and learning will grow. It will assist in flexibility, increases accessibility, allows faculty to track and improve student engagement, boosts student retention, enhances communication as well as peer support, enables and can be cost-effective while scaling up efficiency.

Teaching staff in educational institutions will require technical fluency

For the new trend of online teaching and learning we need a well-developed and advanced infrastructure of relevant platforms and technologies, also there is a need to invest in faculty development and support. One of the greatest challenges in the abrupt transition to fully remote learning during the coronavirus, pandemic was the lack of fluency in the tools of teaching online. So after the pandemic, institutions will need to invest in teacher training and might also invest in creating centralized units to support faculty development efforts.

Way out for Internet shutdown in Jammu and Kashmir

Being a sensitive state J&K faces frequent internet shutdowns, but now the Authorities must take decisions of

the internet shutdowns keeping in view the present Covid-19 pandemic and in the interest of millions of students. The educational websites must be allowed so that the loss of studies can be prevented and students can avail the benefits from these sites. The students of J&K have suffered a lot during the crisis of Covid-19 and even before this due to non-availability of the internet access and schools closures post article 370 abrogation. The union territory of Jammu and Kashmir is still far behind from the modern digital technology to carry out the teaching and learning process in such a pandemic. The administration of the UT of J&K must take such steps and decisions that will be helpful in the modern online distance education and in improving digital infrastructure throughout the union territory.

Administration of Union territory of Jammu and Kashmir must come forward for finding out the alternatives to traditional educational system, and make it possible to continue the studies of the millions of students in the challenging time of Covid-19. The Indian government must aid the J&K union territory so that, millions of students will be able to continue their normal course of studies. In this challenging time of covid-19 pandemic only distance education through online mode is the way to continue the education system. Need of the present time is to develop the information and communication technological infrastructures, like computers, 4G/5G internet, digital gadgets, laptops, smartphones, Television and radio across urban and rural areas. After Covid-19 educational institutions must work together to transform the educational system, proper curriculum of institutions must be designed to recover lost portion with learning strategies and advanced techniques.

Conflicts of Interest

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